

PECULIARITIES OF ULTRASOUND DIAGNOSIS OF MISSION OF PREGNANCY IN ANTIPHOSPHOLIPID SYNDROME

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RELEVANCE. Despite the well-known successes achieved in perinatology, the frequency of spontaneous abortions does not have a significant downward trend and, according to various authors, is 5-12%. In antiphospholipid syndrome, the involvement of ultrasound and diagnostic indicators of the gestation process have not been fully studied. Studying the process of embryogenesis, it is noted that the main morphostructure of gestation is the so-called yolk sac, which should be detected as an extra-amniotic structure of a rounded shape. Often, the yolk sac is an important indicator in diagnosing threatened miscarriage. But it should be noted whether this is also the case with the pathology of pregnancy caused by the antiphospholipid syndrome.

The aim of the study was to determine the difference in the frequency of abortions of yolk sac data in antiphospholipid syndrome and practically healthy pregnancy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. The study was conducted in 61 pregnant women up to 8 weeks of pregnancy. Patients were examined on the basis of the 2nd maternity complex of the city of Andijan together with the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology No. 2. The study included 15 practically healthy pregnant women (control group) and 46 pregnant women with identified antiphospholipid syndrome (main group). This study was approved by the Committee for the Protection of Motherhood and Childhood of the Andijan State Medical Institute.

RESEARCH RESULT. We performed a 2D abdominal ultrasound examination of consecutive pregnancies at 5 to 8 weeks' gestation as part of a routine examination or other indication for ultrasound examination. The size of the yolk sac (internal diameter), shape, echogenicity of the edge and center of the sac, amount of yolk sac, and degenerative changes such as calcification were assessed.

THE DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS. Regarding abnormal characteristics of the yolk sac, 29% of the main group had yolk sacs larger than 6.5 mm; the largest was 7.4 mm in a patient who had four recurrent miscarriages. Of those studied, 18.2% had a distorted yolk sac that resulted in spontaneous abortion in 9.9% who were between 6 and 8 weeks pregnant. However, 2 others continued with full-term, normal live births.

In the control group, abortion was not observed and all pregnancies ended in term delivery. Regarding the characteristics of the yolk sac of the control group, the diameters of the sacs ranged from 3 to 4.3 mm, all of which were round in shape.

FINDINGS. Thus, among the characteristics of the yolk sac, in antiphospholipid syndrome, large size and distorted shape are assumed to be the most important factors for spontaneous abortion already in early gestation.

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